

Experiment : Campbell 12-06-21
 Specimen : Specimen_002
 Tube : NTSR1
 Sort Layout : Sort Layout_001
 Application : FACSDiva Version 8.0.1

Sort Report

Report Date : 2021.12.06 at 15:37:06
 Device : 4 Tube
 User ID : Administrator
 Cytometer : FACSAriaIII (1)

Sort Settings

Sort Setup	70 micron	Precision	4-Way Purity
Frequency	86.0	Yield Mask	0
Amplitude	14.8	Purity Mask	32
Phase	0.00	Phase Mask	0
Drop Delay	46.91	Single Cell	Off
Attenuation	Off	Plates Voltage	5,000
Sweet Spot	On	Voltage Centering	0
First Drop	181	Sheath Pressure	70.00
Target Gap	12		

Side Stream Voltage (%)

Far Left	Left	Right	Far Right
0.00	41.00	34.00	0.00

Neighboring Drop Charge (%)

2nd	3rd	4th
17.00	10.00	0.00

Acquisition Counters

Threshold Count	5120102
Processed Events Count(evt)	5055841
Electronic Aborts Count(evt)	47729
Sort Elapsed Time(hh:mm:ss)	00:14:17

Sort Counters

	Far Left	Left	Right	Far Right
Sort Rate(evt/s)	NA	36	NA	NA
Conflicts Count(evt)	NA	1193	NA	NA
Conflicts Rate(evt/s)	NA	1	NA	NA
Efficiency(%)	NA	96	NA	NA

Sort Layout

Far Left	Left	Right	Far Right
	++ : 31122		